

Farmers Perceptions on Artificial Insemination (AI): A Mixed Method Design

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Abstract:

This study investigated the perceptions of Meranao farmers in Lanao del Sur province about reproductive biotechnology, specifically AI. A cross-sectional descriptive survey employing a mixed-method design of a qualitative-quantitative methodological triangulation was employed in the study involving 203 participants (farmers). The selection of the participants was based on purposive sampling and snowball techniques. Furthermore, the principle of saturation was also applied in the collection of data. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive, correlational statistics, and variance through SPSS version 16. Findings revealed that Artificial Insemination (AI) is not usually known and practice by the livestock raisers in Lanao del Sur. Most of the farmers has no knowledge about AI and it is not promoted in their municipality. Farmers adoptions of AI is influence by different factors such as their lack of knowledge resulted to some misconceptions about. However, findings also showed that they are

willing to adopt AI as long as they are well educated about it. The farmers profile such as age, gender, educational attainment, livestock raise and years of experience in raising livestock significantly influence to their perceptions on AI. It is also shown that there was a significant difference on the perceptions of the farmers towards their awareness and acceptability of AI, and their perceptions about the status and prospect of AI in the province. Based on the findings, it shows that the farmers have no knowledge about AI but they are willing to be trained and adopt the technology as long as they will know about it. Farmers perceptions towards AI in terms of awareness, acceptability, status and prospects are directly influenced by their profile such as age, education, livestock raise, number of livestock and the years of experience in rearing livestock. This implies that, if they will be exposed to trainings and seminars about AI they can

learn the technology and be willing to adopt. As such, this study designed a training program to educate the farmers about AI.

Keywords: *perceptions, artificial insemination, Lanao del Sur.*

Introduction

Reproductive biotechnology plays a great role in farming and livestock production. One of the considered as among the first biotechniques that was developed and adopted by livestock industries to enhance reproductive efficiency of domesticated animals was the artificial insemination (AI). AI as reproductive biotechnology has been widely used particularly in advance countries and has proven to improve many aspects of the industry, including fertility, genetic, biosecurity and production efficiency. However, despite of its promising advantages, still many underdeveloped countries like the Philippines has not fully adopted and promoted AI (Soriano et al., 2021). Reproductive biotechnology is commonly used for diverse livestock species all over the world to enhance reproduction. Animal biotechnology began more than 8000 years to modify and enhance production of livestock. Since animal domestication, many technologies have been developed to make breeding easier, to obtain desirable qualities of offspring and produce more offspring using advance reproductive biotechnology such as artificial insemination (AI), in vitro fertilization (IVF), embryo flushing and cloning (Schook et al., 2014). Biotechnology had and has always have major impact on animal breeding and genetic progress (Gengler & Druet, 2006).

Reproductive biotechnologies have emerged and started to replace the conventional techniques of reproduction. These techniques are imperative to use for sustained livestock productivity, and improve livestock species reproductive efficiency (Choudhary et al., 2016). Reproductive biotechnology is one of the options which have a role in the improvement of livestock, offering numerous advantages to livestock production through enhancement and control of reproductive processes in animals. It

also offers dramatic effect on the world's economy through the improvement of livestock genetics, preventing disease, facilitate transportation, keeping endangered animals and reducing economic loss (Hadgu & Fesseha, 2020). Research studies also showed the contributions of biotechnology to food security. Animal biotechnologies related to reproduction have contributed to many improvements in agriculturally important traits in livestock (Hernandez Gifford & Gifford, 2013), it is very important in developing country (Bedasa et al., 207). Other researchers also claimed that artificial insemination (AI) has several advantages not only in pigs but also to other livestock compared to natural breeding due to its efficiency, effectiveness in introducing of improved germplasm and control of venereal diseases (Knox, 2016; Maes et al., 2008; Sharma et al., 2021). AI has the potential to enhance the traditional backyard livestock production system particularly among pigs (Kadirvel et al., 2012; Palinkas et al., 2015; Patra et al., 2014). Among various dairy innovations in India, artificial insemination (AI) has been considered as an important dairy innovation of socio-economic importance in Indian dairy industry (Rathod et al., 2017).

Studies have been conducted in other countries about farmers attitudes and preferences toward reproductive biotechnology application. Their findings showed that the respondents expressed a positive attitude toward reproductive biotechnology application preferably artificial insemination. However, despite of their positive attitudes towards reproductive biotechnology, they still have some reservation and hesitation due to lack of information, knowledge and practical exposure, absence of peer influence, perceived beliefs and risks, poverty situations, and gender issues (Abigaba et al., 2022). The acceptance of animal biotechnology of any

products hinges on consumer acceptance due to various factors such as moral status of animals, the aspect of “natural” and “unnatural,” the perceived risks and benefits to health and the environment, the purpose and methods being used, the species being modified, and the knowledge and information about the technology (Mushonga et al., 2017).

Several studies also conducted about artificial insemination (AI) as reproductive biotechnological tools. Findings of the study (Soriano et al., 2021) revealed that tribal farmers of Nagaland have favorable attitude towards the technology and strong intent to adopt artificial insemination in pig. Some hesitations were driven by behavioral control that constructs for the intention to adopt artificial insemination in pig, and are affected by farming context especially distance to artificial insemination provider center, concluded that in general, farmers in Zambia, show positive attitudes toward reproductive biotechnology application. However, there is still a need to further promote this technology to gain more favorable attitudes of the farmers, despite the overwhelming preference of farmers for AI, efforts to promote AI-supporting reproductive technologies are required because they contribute to AI success rate (Abigaba et al., 2022). Efficient reproductive performance is very important for sustainability in any livestock production system, especially for milk, meat, draft, and replacement animals. Increasing challenges and opportunities are promising due to advance reproductive biotechnology. The use of modern reproductive technologies has opened many avenues to study, treat and manipulate the reproductive phenomenon both in vitro and in vivo to improve reproductive performance in various domestic species of livestock (Choudhary et al., 2016). Despite of these factors, modern reproductive biotechnology offers great advances and benefits in modifying organisms to increase productions and quality through enhancement and control of reproductive process in animals offering a tremendous satisfaction of the increasing demands of the modern dairy and beef industries (Hadgu & Fesseha, 2020).

In the Philippines, one of the constraints in the development of dairy industry in the country is the limited number of dairy animals. In the Philippines the use of AI increases the conception rate to 60.29% from 37.50% (Soriano et al., 2021). This result, implied that artificial insemination (AI) has the ability to maximize the use of superior sires which has been considered as its greatest advantage. conducted a survey on the “Profile and artificial insemination practices of technicians and the artificial insemination success rates in Leyte, Samar, and Biliran, Philippines in 2011-2015. Their findings pointed out that AI success rate was influence by various factors such the technician profile, and practices of AI technician. It was also noted that the AI success rate recorded highest in 2011 and lowest in 2015 (Warfa, A.M. 2016).

Despite of the promising advantages of reproductive biotechnology and even if it is proven to be effective to change livestock production status of the countries, they are not applied routinely due to the presence of different challenges and different perceptions among farmers. As such, this study aims to investigate the perceptions of Meranao farmers in Lanao del Sur in terms of their awareness and acceptability of AI, and perceptions about the status and prospect of AI in the province.

Methods

Research Design

The study aimed to investigate the purposively selected Meranao farmers in selected Municipalities in district 1 and 2, Lanao del Sur about AI. A cross-sectional descriptive survey employing a mixed-method design of a qualitative-quantitative methodological triangulation was used to determine the socio-demographic information, and perceptions of farmers about AI in relation to its application in cattle production. The design employed a pragmatic approach through the complementarity of the findings from survey, interviews and focus group discussions to permit the breadth and depth of understanding about

the subject matter and enable data collection within a short period (Patra et al., 2014; Ybañez et al., 2017).

Participants of the Study

The study was carried out using survey and interview from April to May 2023, involving 203 farmers who are a livestock raiser, resident in the province with an accessible and have stable peace condition, and willing to participate the study. The municipalities and distribution of participants is shown in Table 1. The municipalities were selected based on its accessibility and stable peace condition, while the participants were selected based on the inclusion criteria mentioned and with the use of purposive and snowball sampling.

Table 1. Respondents Distribution per Municipality

Municipality Name	District	Number of Respondents
Picong	2	31
Marantao & Banga	1	20
Ganasi	2	10
Madamba	2	10
Masiu	1	20

Poonabayabao	1	20
Piagapo	1	25
Lumbatan	2	29
Lumbayanague	2	38
Total		203

Data Collection and Tools

Data on the socio-demographics of the participants was collected using a survey questionnaire. Likewise, another survey questionnaire in Likert scale was used to collect data on farmers perceptions on the use of advance reproductive biotechnology which is the Artificial Insemination (AI). Additional research gathering tools was an interview guide questions which is an open-ended question used to interview the farmers participants to ensure in-depth data collection and analysis. The design of the instrument for the questionnaire survey was based on previous studies related to reproductive biotechnology applications of Klop, T. and Severiens, S. (2007), Amin, Azlan, Hamdan, Samian, and Haron, (2011), but generally the concepts and items was modified with additions and omissions to suit the research topic and the nature of the participants.

Figure 1. Age Profile of the Participants

Statistical Analysis

Quantitative data obtain from 203 farmer participants was analyzed using the statistical software SPSS 16 version. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation the profile and perceptions of the farmers participants. Correlational statistic

was used to determine the relationship between variables while analysis of variance and poshoc test was used to determine if there are differences on the farmers with regards to their perceptions towards AI. Qualitative data from interview was transcribed, summarized, and used to support the discussion of the findings.

Figure 2. Gender Profile of the Participants

Figure 3. Educational Attainment of the Participants

Figure 4. Years of Rearing Livestock of the Participants

Results

Participants' Profile

The profile of the participants such as age, gender, educational attainment and years of experience in rearing livestock is presented in Figure 1-4. As shown in figure 2, the participants have varying age but considerably most of them are above 30 years old. The results also showed

that mostly were male, elementary level, except for Piagapo participants who are mostly graduated in elementary, and mostly have more than five years of experience in rearing livestock as shown in Figure 2-4 respectively. Based on the data it can be said that majority of the participants are has been long livestock growers and have experienced enough on rearing their livestock, regardless of their age and educational attainment.

Figure 5. Livestock Raise by the Participants

Figure 6. Number of Heads of Livestock per Municipality

Figure 7. Reproductive Method Used by the Participants in Each Municipality

Participants Livestock Profile

The livestock profile of the participants in terms of the type of livestock they raise, the number of heads and the reproduction method they usually use are presented in Figure 5-7. Based on the results, cattle are the most prominent livestock that the participants usually reared. Other livestock they raise are buffalo, goat and horse but it is not their major livestock reared. However, in terms of the number heads, Picong raise goat more than cattle, while the rest

municipalities have higher number of cattle raised, except for Masiu and Poonabayabao indicating that the buffalo is greater in number than cattle, goat and horse. However, regardless on the type and number of their livestock the participants unanimously have natural reproduction method for their livestock, except for Marantao that are very few experienced using artificial insemination method.

Perceptions of the Participant About Artificial Insemination (AI)

The perceptions of Meranao livestock raiser in terms of their awareness, acceptability, status and prospect about artificial insemination (AI) were surveyed and the results is shown in graph using mean and standard deviation.

As shown in Figure 8, all participants from selected 9 municipalities agreed that they have no knowledge about artificial insemination, no experience at all and even afraid to use it. Of the five statement all participants unanimously agree indicating a mean of 4.14 and standard deviation of 1.09, (Table 2, Annex 1), that they are not aware about artificial insemination. However, in terms of acceptability, results showed that the majority strongly agree on the statements about acceptability (mean = 4.22, sd = 0.96), which imply that they are very interested to learn more about AI, and willing to try AI, except for the participants in Maranatao-Banga and Piagapo who are not decided yet. Based on interview they said that it's nice to try AI to produce good quality animals except for Madamba participants who are still undecided. Many of them also agreed that they are bounded to their religion

that is why they are hesitating to use AI. Similarly, many of them also agreed that they are hesitant to use AI because it is expensive and have limited knowledge about it, while few are still undecided. In general, in terms of acceptability having a mean of 4.22 (Table 3, Annex 1), imply that they unanimously agree on trying the AI as their reproductive method to be used if there is available in their municipality.

In terms the status of AI, majority strongly agree (Figure 8), that there are no AI services in their municipality, and no expert person to handle such technology, no information dissemination and orientation about AI in their area, except for Madamba that they are not sure about it. In the same manner, majority of the participants, except for Madamba and Picong unanimously agreed that there are no AI programs and the government does not promote or give support to them as to this technology. In general, the participants perceived that the status of the AI technology as a reproductive method still did not exists in their respective municipalities having a mean of 4.43 and a standard deviation of 0.92 (Table 4, Annex 1).

Legend: SDA = strongly disagree DA= disagree U = undecided A= Agree SA = Strongly agree

Figure 8. Farmers Perceptions About Artificial Insemination

In the aspect on prospect or vision majority strongly agree (Figure 8), that AI is a good reproductive method to increase the rate of conception of their livestock, as long as they are all well oriented about the AI technology. They also firmly agreed, that as farmers/livestock raisers, they should adopt modern technology provided that they are well oriented and have enough knowledge about it. As such, they agreed that they need to know and learn about AI as reproductive method and as long as the government has promoted about such technology in their municipality, they are willing to adopt it. Only the participants from Poonabayabao are undecided to adopt AI if there is a government program promoting it. Regardless of varying perceptions, all

participants unanimously agreed the possible adoption of AI to increase their livestock reproduction rate with a mean of 4.5 (agree) and standard deviation of 0.66 (Table 5, Annex 1).

Relationship Between the Profile of the Participants and Their Perceptions Towards Artificial Insemination

Table 6 shows the results of correlating the participants and livestock profile such age, gender, educational attainment, livestock raise, and years of experience in raising the livestock respectively.

Table 6. Relationship Between Participants Profile and Their Perceptions Towards AI (n-203)

		AWARENESS	ACCEPTABILITY	STATUS	PROSPECT
AGE	Pearson Correlation	.797**	.853**	.792**	.838**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
GENDER	Pearson Correlation	-.066	-.045	-.014	-.027
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.353	.522	.837	.701
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	Pearson Correlation	.487**	.475**	.482**	.443**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
LIVESTOCK RAISE	Pearson Correlation	.208**	.133	.202**	.249**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.058	.004	.000
YEARS OF EXPERIENCE	Pearson Correlation	.739**	.701**	.720**	.684**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results computed from Pearson correlation indicated that age, educational attainment, livestock raise, and year of experience in raising their livestock is positively correlated to their perceptions in terms of awareness, acceptability, status and prospect. The results also showed that their gender does not affect their perceptions.

Comparison of Participants Perceptions About AI

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the varying opinions of the

participants regarding to their perceptions about AI as to their awareness, acceptability, perceived status and prospects. Table 7 shows that, the perceptions of the participants in terms of the awareness, acceptance, status and prospect about AI are significantly differ at $\alpha = 0.01$ level of significance. This implies that the participants perceptions vary from each municipality. To determine which municipality shows significant difference on the participants perceptions, Post Hoc test was established using Least Significant Difference (LSD) test, and the results are shown in Table 8, 9 10, and 11.

Table 7. ANOVA Table Showing the Significant Difference of the Participants Perceptions About AI

ANOVA (n=203)						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
AWARENESS	Between Groups	68.764	8	8.596	9.763	.000
	Within Groups	170.802	194	.880		
ACCEPTABILITY	Between Groups	36.651	8	4.581	5.990	.000
	Within Groups	148.373	194	.765		
STTAUS	Between Groups	52.270	8	6.534	10.600	.000
	Within Groups	119.582	194	.616		
PROSPECT	Between Groups	15.263	8	1.908	5.178	.000
	Within Groups	71.485	194	.368		

Table 8, 9, 10 and 11 shows that not all perceptions of the participants in each municipality shows significant difference based on the computed LSD mean difference. Statistically, the mean difference that has a significant (sig) value of equal or lower than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$), indicates the significant difference. In the above mention tables, numerical value that shows significant difference was highlighted for easy reference to identify which municipalities had shown significant difference with regards to their perceptions as to awareness, acceptability, status and prospect about AI. During interview, they also mentioned different views whether to accept AI, and they viewed the status and prospect of AI almost similar with each other. However, out of 2003 participants, only 3 had experienced about AI. The rest of the

participants are not aware about AI, and they said that it is their first time to heard about it. In the aspect of acceptability, almost all of them are willing to accept and adopt AI as their reproductive method with the conditions that they are well informed and become knowledgeable about the technology. In terms of the status and prospect about AI, almost all of the participants had similar views, stating that there is no AI technology in their municipality and their Local Government Unit does not promote AI at all. Likewise, almost ll of them believed that AI is a good and promising technology to enhance their livestock productions in the future. According to them, AI can bring more income to them and makes their livestock healthier.

Table 8. LSD Table for Participants Awareness About AI (n=203)

Dependent Variable	(I) Participants	(J) Participants	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Awareness	Picong	Madamba	-0.67419*	.050	-1.3472	-.0012
		Marantao	-.12419	.645	-.6550	.4066
		Ganasi	-.57419	.094	-1.2472	.0988
		Piagapo	-1.01419*	.000	-1.5116	-.5167
		Poonabayabao	-1.57419*	.000	-2.1050	-1.0434
		Masiu	-1.62419*	.000	-2.1550	-1.0934
		Lumbatan	-1.46385*	.000	-1.9419	-.9858
		Lumbayanague	-1.06367*	.000	-1.5115	-.6158
	Madamba	Marantao	.55000	.132	-.1667	1.2667
		Ganasi	.10000	.812	-.7276	.9276
		Piagapo	-.34000	.334	-1.0324	.3524
		Poonabayabao	-.90000*	.014	-1.6167	-.1833
		Masiu	-.95000*	.010	-1.6667	-.2333

		Lumbatan	-.78966*	.023	-1.4683	-.1110
		Lumbayanague	-.38947	.244	-1.0472	.2682
	Marantao	Ganasi	-.45000	.217	-1.1667	.2667
		Piagapo	-.89000*	.002	-1.4452	-.3348
		Poonabayabao	-1.45000*	.000	-2.0352	-.8648
		Masiu	-1.50000*	.000	-2.0852	-.9148
		Lumbatan	-1.33966*	.000	-1.8775	-.8018
		Lumbayanague	-.93947*	.000	-1.4507	-.4282
	Ganasi	Piagapo	-.44000	.212	-1.1324	.2524
		Poonabayabao	-1.00000*	.006	-1.7167	-.2833
		Masiu	-1.05000*	.004	-1.7667	-.3333
		Lumbatan	-.88966*	.010	-1.5683	-.2110
		Lumbayanague	-.48947	.144	-1.1472	.1682
	Piagapo	Poonabayabao	-.56000*	.048	-1.1152	-.0048
		Masiu	-.61000*	.031	-1.1652	-.0548
		Lumbatan	-.44966	.081	-.9547	.0554
		Lumbayanague	-.04947	.838	-.5260	.4271
	Poonabayabao	Masiu	-.05000	.866	-.6352	.5352
		Lumbatan	.11034	.686	-.4275	.6482
		Lumbayanague	.51053*	.050	-.0007	1.0218
	Masiu	Lumbatan	.16034	.557	-.3775	.6982
		Lumbayanague	.56053*	.032	.0493	1.0718
	Lumbatan	Lumbayanague	.40018	.085	-.0561	.8565

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 9. LSD Table for Participants Acceptability About AI (n=203)

Dependent Variable	(I) Participants	(J) Participants	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Acceptability	Picong	Madamba	.50323	.115	-.1240	1.1305
		Marantao	.00323	.990	-.4915	.4979
		Ganasi	.10323	.746	-.5240	.7305
		Piagapo	-.17677	.453	-.6404	.2869
		Poonabayabao	-.09677	.700	-.5915	.3979
		Masiu	-.44677	.076	-.9415	.0479
		Lumbatan	-1.09677*	.000	-1.5424	-.6512
		Lumbayanague	-.62309*	.004	-1.0405	-.2056
	Madamba	Marantao	-.50000	.142	-1.1680	.1680
		Ganasi	-.40000	.308	-1.1714	.3714
		Piagapo	-.68000*	.039	-1.3254	-.0346
		Poonabayabao	-.60000	.078	-1.2680	.0680
		Masiu	-.95000*	.006	-1.6180	-.2820
		Lumbatan	-1.60000*	.000	-2.2325	-.9675
		Lumbayanague	-1.12632*	.000	-1.7393	-.5133
		Marantao	Ganasi	.10000	.768	-.5680
	Piagapo		-.18000	.493	-.6974	.3374
	Poonabayabao		-.10000	.718	-.6454	.4454
	Masiu		-.45000	.105	-.9954	.0954
	Lumbatan		-1.10000*	.000	-1.6013	-.5987
	Lumbayanague		-.62632*	.010	-1.1028	-.1498
	Ganasi	Piagapo	-.28000	.393	-.9254	.3654
		Poonabayabao	-.20000	.556	-.8680	.4680
		Masiu	-.55000	.106	-1.2180	.1180
		Lumbatan	-1.20000*	.000	-1.8325	-.5675
		Lumbayanague	-.72632*	.020	-1.3393	-.1133

	Piagapo	Poonabayabao	.08000	.761	-.4374	.5974
		Masiu	-.27000	.305	-.7874	.2474
		Lumbatan	-.92000*	.000	-1.3907	-.4493
		Lumbayanague	-.44632*	.049	-.8905	-.0021
	Poonabayabao	Masiu	-.35000	.207	-.8954	.1954
		Lumbatan	-1.00000*	.000	-1.5013	-.4987
		Lumbayanague	-.52632*	.031	-1.0028	-.0498
	Masiu	Lumbatan	-.65000*	.011	-1.1513	-.1487
		Lumbayanague	-.17632	.466	-.6528	.3002
	Lumbatan	Lumbayanague	.47368*	.029	.0484	.8990

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 10. LSD Table for Participants Perceived Status About AI (n=203)

Dependent Variable	(I) Participants	(J) Participants	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Status	Picong	Madamba	.31613	.270	-.2470	.8793
		Marantao	1.11613*	.000	.6720	1.5602
		Ganasi	.21613	.450	-.3470	.7793
		Piagapo	.59613*	.005	.1799	1.0124
		Poonabayabao	-.03387	.881	-.4780	.4102
		Masiu	.36613	.106	-.0780	.8102
		Lumbatan	-.48387*	.018	-.8839	-.0838
		Lumbayanague	-.48387*	.012	-.8586	-.1091
	Madamba	Marantao	.80000*	.009	.2003	1.3997
		Ganasi	-.10000	.776	-.7925	.5925
		Piagapo	.28000	.342	-.2994	.8594
		Poonabayabao	-.35000	.251	-.9497	.2497
		Masiu	.05000	.870	-.5497	.6497
		Lumbatan	-.80000*	.006	-1.3678	-.2322
	Marantao	Lumbayanague	-.80000*	.005	-1.3503	-.2497
		Ganasi	-.90000*	.003	-1.4997	-.3003
		Piagapo	-.52000*	.028	-.9845	-.0555
		Poonabayabao	-1.15000*	.000	-1.6397	-.6603
		Masiu	-.75000*	.003	-1.2397	-.2603
		Lumbatan	-1.60000*	.000	-2.0501	-1.1499
	Ganasi	Lumbayanague	-1.60000*	.000	-2.0278	-1.1722
		Piagapo	.38000	.197	-.1994	.9594
		Poonabayabao	-.25000	.412	-.8497	.3497
		Masiu	.15000	.622	-.4497	.7497
		Lumbatan	-.70000*	.016	-1.2678	-.1322
	Piagapo	Lumbayanague	-.70000*	.013	-1.2503	-.1497
		Poonabayabao	-.63000*	.008	-1.0945	-.1655
		Masiu	-.23000	.330	-.6945	.2345
		Lumbatan	-1.08000*	.000	-1.5026	-.6574
	Poonabayabao	Lumbayanague	-1.08000*	.000	-1.4788	-.6812
		Masiu	.40000	.109	-.0897	.8897
		Lumbatan	-.45000	.050	-.9001	.0001
	Masiu	Lumbayanague	-.45000*	.039	-.8778	-.0222
		Lumbatan	-.85000*	.000	-1.3001	-.3999
	Lumbatan	Lumbayanague	-.85000*	.000	-1.2778	-.4222
		Lumbatan	.00000	1.000	-.3818	.3818

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 11. LSD Table for Participants Perceived Prospect About AI (n=203)

Dependent Variable	(I) Participants	(J) Participants	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Prospect	Picong	Madamba	.25161	.256	-.1838	.6870
		Marantao	.35161*	.045	.0082	.6950
		Ganasi	.15161	.493	-.2838	.5870
		Piagapo	.25161	.125	-.0702	.5734
		Poonabayabao	.10161	.560	-.2418	.4450
		Masiu	-.24839	.155	-.5918	.0950
		Lumbatan	-.44494*	.005	-.7542	-.1356
		Lumbayanague	-.31154*	.035	-.6013	-.0218
	Madamba	Marantao	.10000	.671	-.3637	.5637
		Ganasi	-.10000	.713	-.6354	.4354
		Piagapo	.00000	1.000	-.4480	.4480
		Poonabayabao	-.15000	.524	-.6137	.3137
		Masiu	-.50000*	.035	-.9637	-.0363
		Lumbatan	-.69655*	.002	-1.1356	-.2575
		Lumbayanague	-.56316*	.010	-.9887	-.1377
	Marantao	Ganasi	-.20000	.396	-.6637	.2637
		Piagapo	-.10000	.584	-.4592	.2592
		Poonabayabao	-.25000	.194	-.6286	.1286
		Masiu	-.60000*	.002	-.9786	-.2214
		Lumbatan	-.79655*	.000	-1.1445	-.4486
		Lumbayanague	-.66316*	.000	-.9939	-.3324
	Ganasi	Piagapo	.10000	.660	-.3480	.5480
		Poonabayabao	-.05000	.832	-.5137	.4137
		Masiu	-.40000	.090	-.8637	.0637
		Lumbatan	-.59655*	.008	-1.0356	-.1575
		Lumbayanague	-.46316*	.033	-.8887	-.0377
	Piagapo	Poonabayabao	-.15000	.411	-.5092	.2092
		Masiu	-.50000*	.007	-.8592	-.1408
		Lumbatan	-.69655*	.000	-1.0233	-.3698
		Lumbayanague	-.56316*	.000	-.8715	-.2549
	Poonabayabao	Masiu	-.35000	.070	-.7286	.0286
		Lumbatan	-.54655*	.002	-.8945	-.1986
		Lumbayanague	-.41316*	.015	-.7439	-.0824
	Masiu	Lumbatan	-.19655	.267	-.5445	.1514
		Lumbayanague	-.06316	.707	-.3939	.2676
	Lumbatan	Lumbayanague	.13339	.374	-.1618	.4286

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Discussion

The descriptive statistical analysis indicated that the personal profile of the participants in terms of age, educational attainment and years of experience in raising livestock were almost similar. It shows that most of them are age 30 years old and above, male, only gained elementary education, and with more than five year of experience in livestock raising.

Considering that they have limited educational attainment, it may imply that they also have limited knowledge about reproductive technology like artificial insemination despite of having more than five years of experience in raising their livestock. Based on the interviews conducted, all of them except for three individuals in Banga claimed that they never heard about artificial insemination. Likewise,

they also have no experience about the technology. Their common statement is that they don't know about artificial insemination, and they are afraid of using that technology since they are unfamiliar with AI. However, they are willing to try the technology once they are trained and well informed about AI. Farmers' idea about AI varied according to farmers' characteristics and farm structure, and these factors are found to significantly affect the probability of a farmer adopting AI as agricultural innovation. In order for the farmers to willingly adopt AI, a model of dairy farmers' utilization of AI reproductive techniques must be developed specifically, modelling the farm factors driving the uptake of AI enables the understanding of the differences between various types of landowners (Howley et al., 2012).

On the other hand, farmers are also hesitant to adopt AI due to its cost and service delivery. Upon interview, the participants mentioned that there is no available AI service in their municipality and their Local Government Unit, does not promote AI. Farmers preferred the public departments through veterinary dispensary and sub-center artificial insemination service because it is cheap, quality and timely delivery of service coupled with better conception rate (Karthikeyan et al., 2018). The feelings of the farmers were generally neutral despite the favorable assessment of their opinions and behavioral intentions toward biotechnology use. The potential for acceptance and widespread popularity of several AI-supporting reproductive biotechnologies given due attention to the views and perspectives of the participants regarding the perceived barriers and approaches to more favorable attitudes (Abigaba et al., 2022).

Results of the study revealed a positive and significant relationship of the participants' profile and their perceptions towards artificial insemination, except for gender that it does not influence their awareness, acceptability and their perceived status and prospect about artificial insemination. The relationship between age, educational attainment, livestock raise and their number of years in raising their livestock has

positive relations to their perceptions as to awareness, acceptability, status and prospect about artificial insemination. This implies that the higher the age, educational attainment, livestock and years of experience, the more they perceived to adopt artificial insemination. The relationship of these variables is very highly significant at $\alpha=0.01$ level of significance. Other research findings reported that the adoption of breeding technology is related to various factors such as educational level of farmers, and age (Khanal & Gillespie, 2011). The more educated the farmers are it is more likely to adopt advanced breeding technologies such as AI, sexed semen and embryo transplants. However, farm level cost of AI services, farming experience, herd size and breed of animals are negatively associated with adoption and use of AI technology (Kaaya et al., 2005). Assessing technician's profile and their AI practices can be significant in improving AI success rate (Warfa, A.M. 2016).

Research studies have shown various reasons and factors with regard to adoption of AI as reproductive technology. Research findings showed that AI success rate was influenced by various factors such as the technician profile and practices, as well as the perceptions of the farmers (Rathod et al., 2017), it is also noted that farmers' hesitation towards AI is driven by behavioral control like unavailability of the technology in the community (Sharma et al., 2021), and there is still a need to further promote this technology to gain more favorable attitudes of the farmers (Abigaba et al., 2022).

The results of this study indicating the significant difference on the perceptions of the participants regarding their awareness, acceptability, status and prospect about AI implies that the participants from different municipalities have different perceptions about AI. The farmers' idea about AI varies in accordance to the farmers' characteristics and farm structure (Howley et al., 2012). The adoption of breeding technology is also affected and influenced by educational level and age of the farmers (Khanal & Gillespie, 2011), in which the findings of our study confirmed this finding as well. Several studies also confirmed that there are several factors that influence the adoptability of AI breeding

technology and most of these factors are the level of education of the farmers, family size, distance to AI station and occupation in agriculture or animal husbandry (Mushonga et al., 2017; Patra et al., 2014). Similarly, the findings of this study also confirmed that educational attainment is positively and significantly influence to the farmers perceptions towards AI such as awareness, acceptability, status and prospects. However, this study also found out that the participants has misconceptions about AI. Based on interviews, majority believed that using AI will protect their animals from diseases, and make their livestock healthy. This implies that they have no enough knowledge about AI and not familiar with the AI technology. Based on literature, in the Philippines setting only few researches has been conducted about farmers perceptions about AI which needs attention to some researchers and agricultural sectors to assess the status of AI in the Philippines. Using artificial insemination (AI) as breeding method has the ability to maximize the use of superior sires increases the success rate of conception (Schook et al., 2014). But unfortunately, only few livestock growers applied AI technology.

Conclusion

This study investigated the farmers perceptions on advance reproductive biotechnology specifically as to their awareness, acceptability, status and prospects of artificial insemination in their municipality. Based on the results and discussion it can be said that artificial insemination (AI) is not usually known by the farmers in Lanao del Sur, despite of their long years of experience in raising different livestock, they usually use natural method of reproduction. Their perceptions about AI as to awareness, acceptability, status and prospect is influence by their age, gender, educational attainment, types of livestock raise and their year of experience in raising livestock. Many farmers have misconceptions about AI technology because they have no knowledge about AI and for this, they are hesitant to adopt the said technology. However, despite of their hesitation due to lack

of knowledge almost all of them wanted to try AI as long as they will be educated about the technology.

The lack of knowledge and misconceptions of farmers about AI may be mitigated by providing extension services and programs to their community about AI, and improve service access and delivery of information towards modern reproductive technology to rural farmers. Furthermore, trainings and seminar workshops must be extended to them to make them keep abreast of the advances on dairy and livestock farming. As such, this study recommends, that the MSU College of Agriculture should design extension programs to enhance farmers knowledge about AI and other advances and technologies to improve their livestock production and management.

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Availability of data and materials

All the data analyzed during this study are included in this article.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Ethical Clearance and Informed Consent

The prescribed ethical principles was followed and all policy and guideline documents, permits and consent, and other regulatory bodies, which stipulated ethical practices, such as entry protocol, approval from research ethics committee (etc.) was taken into consideration. These prohibit the researchers from plagiarism, harm or violation of the rights of the involved in the research study. All participants was informed about the study objectives and signed consent was obtained from them.

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Annex 1

Table 2. Participants Awareness on Artificial Insemination (n=203)

Statement	Municipality/Area	SDA		DA		U		A		SA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	f	%	F	%
1) I don't have any knowledge/idea about artificial insemination.	Picong	1	3.23					19	61.3	11	35.5
	Madamba			2	20			5	50	3	30
	Marantao-Banga			6	30			13	65	1	5
	Ganasi			2	20			3	30	5	10
	Piagapo							16	64	9	36
	Poonabayabao							8	40	12	60
	Masiu					2	10	3	15	15	75
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague			5	13.2	1	2.6	3	7.9	29	76.3
2) This is my first time to hear about artificial insemination	Picong	1	3.23					20	64.5	10	32.3
	Madamba			2	20			5	50	3	30
	Marantao-Banga			8	40			10	50	2	10
	Ganasi			3	30			4	40	3	30
	Piagapo							21	84	3	16
	Poonabayabao							6	30	14	70
	Masiu			1	5	2	10	3	15	14	70
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague			3	7.9	4	10.5	6	15.8	25	65.8
3) I am afraid to use AI because I am not familiar with it	Picong	1	3.23	30	96.8						
	Madamba			2	20			5	50	3	30
	Marantao-Banga	2	10	3	15	1	5	12	60	2	10
	Ganasi			2	20			3	30	5	50
	Piagapo					1	4	13	52	11	44
	Poonabayabao							6	30	14	70
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan	3	10.3	5	17.2	6	20.7			15	51.7
	Lumbayanague			5	13.2	3	7.9	8	21.1	22	57.9
4) I don't have any experience in using AI to my cattle/buffalo	Picong	1	3.3			6	19.4	24	77.4		
	Madamba			2	20			4	40	4	40
	Marantao-Banga	1	5	5	25	2	10	8	40	4	20
	Ganasi							5	50	5	50
	Piagapo							16	64	9	36
	Poonabayabao									20	100
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague					8	21.1	5	13.2	25	65.8
5) I am afraid to use AI because it may cause damage to my animals	Picong	1	3.3	30	96.8						
	Madamba			2	20			4	40	4	40
	Marantao-Banga			6	30	5	25	7	35	2	10
	Ganasi			2	20	2	20	2	60		
	Piagapo					3	12	18	72	4	16
	Poonabayabao									20	100

	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague			5	13.2	6	15.8	6	15.8	21	55.3
Mean											4.15
SD											1.09

Table 3. Participants Acceptability of Artificial Insemination (n=203)

Statement	Municipality/Area	SDA		DA		U		A		SA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	f	%	F	%
1) I am very interested to learn more about AI	Picong							1	3.23	30	96.8
	Madamba							4	40	6	60
	Marantao-Banga							14	70	6	30
	Ganasi							2	20	8	80
	Piagapo					1	4	19	76	5	20
	Poonabayabao					6	30	3	15	11	55
	Masiu					7	35	3	15	10	50
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague					3	7.9	1	2.6	34	89.5
2) I am willing to try AI to my animals	Picong							11	35.5	20	64.5
	Madamba			2	20					8	80
	Marantao-Banga							15	75	5	25
	Ganasi					3	30	3	30	4	40
	Piagapo					1	4	19	76	5	20
	Poonabayabao							1	5	19	95
	Masiu					3	15	4	20	13	65
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague					2	5.3	6	15.8	30	78.9
3) I think it is nice to try so that my animal can produce good quality offspring and increase reproduction rate	Picong							22	71	9	29
	Madamba					10	100				
	Marantao-Banga							16	80	4	20
	Ganasi			1	10	2	20	2	20	5	50
	Piagapo					7	28	12	48	6	24
	Poonabayabao					2	10	14	70	4	20
	Masiu					8	40	1	5	11	55
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague					2	2.56	6	15.8	30	78.9
4) I am not willing to use AI because it is not allowed in Islam	Picong					18	58.1			13	41.9
	Madamba					5	50	5	50		
	Marantao-Banga			2	10	5	25	11	55	2	10
	Ganasi			2	20	4	40	2	20	2	20
	Piagapo					11	44	10	40	4	16
	Poonabayabao					12	60	3	15	5	25
	Masiu	6	30			5	25			9	45
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague			3	7.89	2	5.3	3	7.9	30	78.9
	Picong			17	54.8	1	3.23	13	41.9		

5) I am not willing to use AI because it is expensive	Madamba			2	20	8	80				
	Marantao-Banga			2	10	6	30	11	55	1	5
	Ganasi			2	20	3	30	3	30	2	20
	Piagapo					3	12	20	80	2	8
	Poonabayabao					8	40	10	50	2	10
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
6) I don't know if I am going to use AI, it depends on my knowledge and capacity to adopt it.	Lumbayanague			4	10.5	3	7.9	4	10.5	27	71.1
	Picong			17	54.8	1	3.23	13	41.9		
	Madamba					10	100				
	Marantao-Banga			2	10	6	30	10	50	2	10
	Ganasi					4	40	3	30	3	30
	Piagapo					1	4	17	68	7	28
	Poonabayabao					12	60	4	20	4	20
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
Lumbayanague			10	26.3	5	13.2	5	13.2	18	47.4	
Mean											4.22
SD											0.96

Table 4. Status of Artificial Insemination as Perceived by the Participants(n=203)

Statement	Municipality/Area	SDA		DA		U		A		SA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	f	%	F	%
1) There are no available AI services here in our area/province	Picong							31	100		
	Madamba					1	10			9	90
	Marantao-Banga			7	35	3	15	8	40	2	10
	Ganasi					2	20	5	50	3	30
	Piagapo					2	8	20	80	3	12
	Poonabayabao			2	10			12	60	5	25
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague									38	100
2) There is no expert person that can handle AI	Picong			1	3.23			30	96.8		
	Madamba			2	20					8	80
	Marantao-Banga			6	30	3	15	10	50	1	5
	Ganasi					2	20	5	50	3	30
	Piagapo					4	16	12	48	9	36
	Poonabayabao	5	25			12	60	3	15		
	Masiu	9	45			10	50	1	5		
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague									38	100
3) There is no orientation/educational information given to us about AI, so we are not knowledgeable about it	Picong							17	54.8	14	45.2
	Madamba					10	100				
	Marantao-Banga			5	25	3	15	10	50	2	10
	Ganasi					1	10	5	50	4	40
	Piagapo							19	76	6	24
	Poonabayabao									20	100
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100

	Lumbayanague									38	100
4) There are no project/programs about AI in the municipality and maybe in the whole province. I don't know	Picong					13	31.9	18	58.1		
	Madamba					10	100				
	Marantao-Banga			4	20	5	25	10	50	1	5
	Ganasi					1	10	4	40	5	50
	Piagapo					4	24	15	60	4	16
	Poonabayabao									20	100
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague									38	100
5) The government has no support to us as farmers.	Picong	12	38.7	5	16.1	11	35.5	1	3.23	2	6.45
	Madamba					5	50	5	50		
	Marantao-Banga			4	20	5	25	10	50	1	5
	Ganasi					1	10	3	30	6	60
	Piagapo					2	8	19	76	4	16
	Poonabayabao									20	100
	Masiu	11	55	2	10	2	10	2	10	3	15
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague									38	100
Mean											4.43
SD											0.92

Table 5 Prospect of Artificial Insemination as Perceived by the Participants (n=203)

Statement	Municipality/Area	SDA		DA		U		A		SA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	f	%	F	%
1) AI is good so that the reproduction rate of our animals will increase	Picong							21	67.7	10	32.3
	Madamba					4	40			6	60
	Marantao-Banga							19	95	1	5
	Ganasi					2	20	3	30	5	50
	Piagapo			1	4	7	28	11	44	6	24
	Poonabayabao									20	100
	Masiu									29	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague							5	13.2	33	86.8
2) I think AI is good as long we are properly oriented about it.	Picong							25	80.6	6	19.4
	Madamba							19	95	1	5
	Marantao-Banga					5	50			5	50
	Ganasi					2	20	3	30	6	60
	Piagapo					1	4	15	60	9	36
	Poonabayabao									20	100
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan									29	100
	Lumbayanague							5	13.2	33	86.8
3) It is important to adopt modern technology but we need proper orientation and	Picong							14	45.2	17	54.8
	Madamba					4	40			6	60
	Marantao-Banga							18	90	2	10
	Ganasi					1	10	2	20	7	70

trainings about that technology	Piagapo							20	80	5	29
	Poonabayabao							12	60	8	40
	Masiu									20	100
	Lumbatan						11	37.9	18	62.1	
	Lumbayanague						10	26.3	28	73.7	
4) We need to know and learn about AI so that we can decide whether to adopt it or not in the future	Picong						9	29	22	71	
	Madamba				4	40			6	60	
	Marantao-Banga						19	95	1	5	
	Ganasi				1	10	4	40	5	50	
	Piagapo						18	72	7	28	
	Poonabayabao				6	30	11	55	3	15	
	Masiu								20	100	
	Lumbatan								29	100	
	Lumbayanague						10	26.3	28	73.7	
5) If there is a government program promoting AI in our area, maybe we can adopt if it is beneficial to us	Picong						13	41.9	18	58.1	
	Madamba				4	40			6	60	
	Marantao-Banga						19	95	1	5	
	Ganasi				1	10	5	50	4	40	
	Piagapo				2	8	16	64	7	28	
	Poonabayabao				12	60			8	40	
	Masiu						6	20.7	23	79.3	
	Lumbatan			8	40				12	60	
	Lumbayanague						8	21.1	30	78.9	
Mean											4.5
SD											0.67

Annex 2. Proposed Training and Techno-transfer

Training Title: **Seminar on Artificial Insemination (AI) and Reproductive Management in Ruminants**

Training Program Overview

The Artificial Insemination (AI) and reproductive management seminar is a training program designed to enhance farmers knowledge about AI. This seminar focuses on the concepts and benefits of using AI as method of reproductive management. The program will discuss about the basic concepts of AI, the reproductive anatomy and physiology of ruminants and provide the participants opportunity to gain hands on experience in performing a successful AI procedure.

Objectives of the Training

At the end of the seminar the participants are expected to learn;

1. Basic concepts about AI
2. Familiarize AI tools and equipment
3. Handling frozen semen and thawing
4. Basic anatomy of female ruminant reproductive tract
5. Heat detection of ruminants

Program Agenda

- Introduction and Opening Ceremony
- Lecture Series
 - Lecture 1: Ruminants Reproductive Anatomy and Physiology
 - Video Presentation
 - Lecture 2: Heat Detections for Ruminants
 - Lecture 3: Basic Concepts of Artificial Insemination: Advantages & Disadvantages
 - Lecture 3: Tools and Equipment for Artificial Insemination
 - Lecture 4: The Art of Artificial Insemination
 - Video Presentation
 - Activity: AI Demonstration and Hands-on Participation among Participants

Annex 3: Some Documentations During Data Gathering

Piagapo

Lumbatan

Picong

Maranatao